

WAYS OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES ON THE BASIS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation. This article describes the analysis of ways, methods and tools for organizing educational processes on the basis of information technology.

Keywords. Information and communication technologies, information resources, Internet, computer technology, information society.

Broad introduction of new information and communication and pedagogical technologies into the educational process, strengthening the educational and laboratory base of educational institutions, radically improving the quality of education in the schools, professional colleges, lyceums and higher educational institutions of our country on the account of formation of an effective system of material and spiritual stimulation of teachers and mentors' labor, modern information and, to introduce them into the life of each family and its wide development all educational institutions have huge tasks.

Exhibitions on the introduction of information and communication technologies, seminars, conferences, competitions and quizzes, as well as other mass events, the introduction of information and communication technologies in all spheres of life, the promotion of their use in every organization and family, information among children, adolescents and young people – encourage the acquisition of knowledge in the field of communication technologies, increase the attractiveness of work and entrepreneurship in the field of information and communication technologies, especially in the development of software products, further reduce the cost and improve the quality of providing Internet services to the population, including the rural population, gradually increasing access to international channels of the Internet network, creating, provision of backup of Internet channels and their interconnection using satellite communication systems, expansion of wireless broadband network of data transmission in rural areas, development of digital TV broadcasts in the Republic of Uzbekistan together with the possibility of providing Internet services, organization of training system on the basis of Information Technology on the basis of computer classes of educational institutions of the population – on the basis of communication technology, functions such as preparation and distribution of educational multimedia presentation materials are laid out on compact discs for teaching.

In modern society, the productive activity of man is taking place within the framework of generalized production (UICH). UICH consists of information-logical parts of physical (material) concentration, which are inextricably linked with each other. It is known that the countries that gave strength to the information-logical part of production achieved high productivity of work and production of modern, purchased products. The basis of the resources of information-logical production (AMICH) is information, while cocktail means are accounting techniques, its software, information technology, etc. Cocktail tools, as well as people who spend a smart cocktail, who have experience and knowledge, make up the production Forces of Amich. Amich's product manifests itself as a subject of consumption of an abstract object (information, model).

The extensive development of accounting techniques and means of communication has made it possible to collect, store, process and transmit information in a volume and speed that could not have been previously imagined, that is, to process it in an automated state. Thanks to Information Technology, the activity of a person, the sphere of his daily communication are truly unaware of the account of the involvement of experience, knowledge and spiritual values developed by the world civilization. This in turn necessitates the high level of informatization of the society.

In an informed society, not only production, but also the whole lifestyle, the system of values change. In an information society where all actions are directed towards the production and consumption of tokens, intellect, knowledge are produced and consumed, this circumstance leads to an increase in the share of smart cocktails. From man to creativity requires dexterity, the need for knowledge increases.

The material and technological basis of an informed society is a variety of systems based on computer equipment and computer networks, Information Technology, Telecommunication communications.

An informed society is a society in which most members of society are engaged in the production, storage, processing and implementation of information, especially knowledge, which is its supreme form.

In the transition to an Information Society, a new information processing industry is emerging on the basis of computer and telecommunication information technology.

At present, the same thing is becoming clear that in order for this or that country to occupy a worthy place in the 21st century and participate equally in the economic competition with other countries, it is necessary to reconstruct its economic structure, priorities, wealth, institutions and adapt its industry to the requirements of Information Systems.

Our Republic is also entering into the information society due to its independence. This issue is among the first issues in the spotlight of the president and the government.

The implementation of such efforts creates an opportunity to further accelerate the wide application of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, to arm professors and teachers with advanced pedagogical knowledge and technologies, to improve their skills, to deeply study the experience of foreign higher education institutions, and to introduce effective methods and tools in them into our national education system.

One of the main ways to improve the quality and effectiveness of the educational system will be the involvement of highly qualified personnel in the development of modern information communication technologies, including the use of multimedia training courses, the provision of interactive interaction of the teacher and the student, the development of multimedia training courses and textbooks. Multimedia is a modern information technology, which is developing proudly. Just as textbooks are used, in the application of multimedia tools, educational strategies can be enriched with content only when the teacher in the educational process is engaged in providing not only information, but also in facilitating, supporting and managing the learning process. As a rule, presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations turn out to be much more attractive than simple-looking texts, and they can provide the necessary emotional level by complementing the materials presented. Multimedia tools can be used in harmony with various educational trends and can be used by individuals with different mental and age characteristics of learning as well as cognitive perception: some educators like to learn and absorb

knowledge through direct reading, others by hearing perception, others by seeing (videographs). The expression in Multimedia technologies in the form of images, sound and movements than in traditional technologies teaches students to be more active, attentive and inquisitive in the lessons, because each of the recommended information is carried out through their participation and movement. In the educational system, multimedia technology is a tool that positively and efficiently affects the students by combining theoretical, practical, visual, educational, and control parts. In addition, the use of multimedia training courses in the educational system makes it possible to create qualitative video recordings of performances of theoretical materials, virtual laboratory works and practices, imitation animation models of various processes, for this purpose it will be necessary to organize practical activities of students in the classrooms, computer classes, room of technical means of teaching, in methodological rooms, libraries.

Multimedia is an effective and promising tool for teaching that provides the teacher with a wider range of information than a traditional source of information; use not only text, graphics, diagrams, but also sound, animations, videos, etc.; allows students to select the types of information in sequence according to their level of perception and logical study.

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